

Fact Sheet

ENVISION's approach to inclusive conservation

A scientific overview and project update

November 2019

This paper summarises the scientific basis for inclusive conservation in the context of protected area management, and provides an update on ENVISION's activities in 2019. It is intended for members of ENVISION's local and inter-site knowledge alliances so that they can better understand the scientific directions of the ENVISION project. The ideas presented in this paper will be further developed over the course of the project based on the data collated and the insights shared by alliance members.

'Inclusive Conservation' is a trans-disciplinary approach to balancing stakeholder visions, and promoting shared agreements for the future management of protected areas. Inclusive conservation involves developing and applying inter- and trans-disciplinary tools and processes to identify, compare and balance the consequences of different visions for how nature should be conserved.

Trends in the management of protected areas and the effectiveness of management actions

Protected areas are the most widely known, well-accepted strategy for conserving biodiversity in the face of land use changes (e.g. ecosystem fragmentation and agricultural intensification), ecosystem pollution and deterioration^{1,2} and a tremendous source of essential and distinctive ecosystem services³. The planet's network of protected areas includes more than 14% of land, 2% of the marine and more than 10% of coastal ecosystems^{4,5,6}. Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity aim to increase the percentage of protected areas coverage through Aichi Target 11, calling for the protection of 17 per cent of terrestrial areas including inland water areas and 10 per cent of coastal and marine areas by 2020. However, the world is not on track to realize these goals, and other Aichi biodiversity targets⁷. While protected areas have had variable successes, many fail to fully maintain their biodiversity⁸, and are poorly resourced⁹, compromising the capacity to provide ecosystem services and human well-being¹⁰. Additionally, global change, land use modifications and pressures from growing population are challenging the expected outcomes from protected areas¹¹.

What are the challenges for the management of protected areas?

Despite progress in coverage by protected areas, several major challenges remain regarding their implementation:

- Exploring differences in visions and levels of support among local and national governments regarding protected area management, and low stakeholder and resident awareness of the benefits of protected areas¹².

- Accounting for the role of other effective conservation measures (OECMs) in conservation policies and research^{13, 14, 15}.
- Balancing societal, economic and policy goals for protected area management^{16, 17}.
- Recognising and assessing the dynamic relationships between people and nature proposed in recent approaches to valuation^{19, 20, 21, 22} in a way that enables effective monitoring of conservation achievements^{23, 24}.
- Investigating the uncertain effect of drivers of change on the conservation of protected areas²⁵, and issues concerning the role of various power relations on the acceptance of protected area management strategies²⁶.
- Navigating plurality and conflict among different approaches to conceptualizing and assessing the diverse values of nature, including intrinsic, instrumental and relational values^{27, 28}, with the goal of better representing the perspectives of scientists and practitioners regarding conservation policies^{29, 30}.
- Assessing, monitoring and integrating social equity and environmental justice, including the rights of multiple actors in protected area management^{31, 32}.
- Disentangling trade-offs and synergies between biodiversity conservation and the provision of ecosystem services within and outside of protected areas^{33, 34, 35}.
- Assessing the influence of landscape scale processes (including feedbacks and flows) on biodiversity and ecosystem service^{36, 37}.
- Evaluating the quantity and quality of protected areas in terms of general sustainability indicators, ecological and area-based measures, social impacts and social justice³⁸.

Addressing these challenges through inclusive conservation

An introduction to ENVISION's approach

Scientists, practitioners, stakeholders and local communities have varying perspectives on what conservation and protected areas entail. A comprehensive consideration of the above-mentioned challenges using an inclusive conservation approach is critical to safeguarding biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human well-being^{39, 40, 41}.

In response, ENVISION is a trans-disciplinary research project that develops, tests, and validates a novel, inclusive scenario approach for engaging multiple stakeholders and local communities in protected area management and biodiversity decision-making at multiple scales (**Figure 1**). We propose that by identifying and balancing these different perspectives and visions, and by understanding the importance of different human values and relationships with nature, we can move towards outcomes which are expected to equally improve social and conservation outcomes in protected areas⁴².

Broadly, the ENVISION project addresses the research questions of: 1) to what extent is balancing diverse visions possible and, 2) how can strategies based on collectively defined visions be translated into protected area management at multiple scales?

Our inclusive approach to conservation

Transforming visions into integrated protected area management strategies; improving biodiversity and human well-being

Considering multiple visions for protected area management

- To compare different understandings of inclusive conservation and visions of protected area management across researchers, protected area managers, industry groups, local communities and policy makers.
- To establish an integrative socio-ecological approach for inclusive conservation that considers multiple visions and scenarios for protected area management, and provides a foundation for knowledge co-creation.

Figure 1: Our ENVISION team will investigate various aspects of exploring visions for management of protected areas, including consequences and trade-offs, social learning, power relations, uncertainty and resilience, and communication

Assessing the consequences of each vision

- To quantitatively assess the consequences of different scenarios and associated visions on biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human well-being by drawing on socio-economic and ecosystem attributes;

Social learning about the consequences of each vision

- To test how, and to what extent, social learning about the consequences of each vision changes values and enables the development of collectively defined visions for protected area management.

Assessing uncertainty and building resilience

- To better understand how uncertainties in the pathways towards collectively defined visions can be dealt with and translated into more resilient protected area management strategies.

Acknowledging power relations and rethinking governance

- To propose inclusive governance models and instruments that are sensitive to power relationships and stakeholders' collectively defined visions, and capable of informing protected area decision-making at multiple scales.

Informing biodiversity and protected area management policy

- To communicate and disseminate project findings to diverse stakeholders within and across study areas. We will support the ongoing development of a post-2020 global biodiversity framework to be adopted by the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity in 2020.

What has ENVISION achieved to date?

ENVISION started in January 2019. In the first 12 months we have conducted the following activities:

Across all sites

- A webinar on inclusive conservation involving 46 members of the public
- A fact sheet on inclusive conservation for policy makers
- Informing important debates as part of focus group discussions on the post-2020 biodiversity agenda, including discussions relating to the formation of the EU Biodiversity framework, and post-2020 Convention of Biological Diversity targets.

Västra Harg nature reserve and the wider Östergötland region, Sweden

- 30 interviews have been conducted with members of the local knowledge alliance to better understand how their knowledge and values relate to their visions for protected area and integrated landscape management.
- Approximately 430 respondents completed a participatory mapping survey that examined the relationships between place-based values and preferences for conservation and protected area management in Mjölby municipality, with a specific focus on strategies for the management of oak woodlands and wild boar.

- Plans have commenced for a wider survey on the differences between scientific and traditional knowledge concerning biodiversity, ecosystems and management of landscapes in the Östergötland region, recognizing that different knowledge systems may have different visions for protected area management
- In the early stages of a social and ecological values modelling activity based on different scenarios of biodiversity, ecosystem services and climate change.

Scientific outputs from these activities will inform landscape resilience assessments in 2020. Knowledge alliance members will be asked to consider cross-scale dynamics that are influencing protected area management based on ENVISION's data and their own experiences. Also, there will be opportunity to discuss the types and levels of uncertainty associated with the different visions for protected area management based on the social and ecological consequences presented through the science.

Sierra de Guadarrama, Spain

- Approximately 35 interviews have been conducted with local knowledge alliance members concerning their place-based values and visions for protected area management, as well as their perceptions of different drivers of landscape change. **STREAMLINE** was used as a tool for eliciting drivers of change.
- An additional 85 interviews have been completed aimed at exploring the networks and relations between institutional members and how governance arrangements and interactions shape Sierra de Guadarrama conservation outcomes.
- More than 200 responses have been received on a survey conducted face-to-face with local residents from the buffer zone of the national park in relation to human values, local ecological knowledge, attitudes and visions about nature conservation and perceptions of inclusive conservation.
- Workshops are being planned for May 2020 to explore how these data can inform different scenarios for the management of Sierra de Guadarrama.

Kromme Rijn and Utrechtse Heuvelrug regions, The Netherlands

- Using the **STREAMLINE** tool approximately 58 interviews have been conducted with recreationists / residents, policy-makers from regional governments and representatives of environmental organizations in order to better understand the perceived importance of different landscape functions, as well as to explore their knowledge of trade-offs and preferences for landscape multi-functionality. These data will be complemented with analysis of policy documents of main stakeholder organizations in the area and more interviews (when need be) in order to identify main visions for the area and integrated landscape management.
- Spatially referenced social and ecological data are currently being collated to inform the modelling of the consequences associated with the dominant stakeholder visions. Workshops are being planned where modelled consequences are presented to stakeholders and new visions as well as pathways to reaching them are identified through deliberation.

Denali National Park, United States

- Meetings have been held with around 100 stakeholders for informal and formal interviews. To date, we have completed 36 semi-structured (recorded) interviews that have explored topics including place meanings, environmental governance, management practices for grappling with landscape change, and knowledge exchange.
- A total of seven focus groups have been held to build an in-depth understanding of the social-ecological landscape around Denali.
- Conducted fuzzy cognitive mapping exercises to identify drivers of change and to understand the mental models of stakeholders around Denali (N=43).
- Expanded our local knowledge alliance to guide our work with community members to include the State of Alaska, federal government, local government, industry, local business, and Alaska Natives.
- Presentations have been given at several venues (e.g., General Assembly meeting for the Denali Borough, community events) to build relationships and raise awareness of the project.

In summary, the ENVISION project is making excellent progress. We look forward to working with the knowledge alliance and other key stakeholders during the next stages of the project.

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